

Quantifying Expected Gains from Implementing a Prognostics Algorithm on Systems with Long Logistics Delay Times

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Abstract— Many modern systems are themselves composed of smaller subsystems, which are composed of individual parts. Most prognostics algorithms attempt to provide a Remaining Useful Life (RUL) value for lower level components. Since the RUL prediction would allow for a replacement component to be requisitioned prior to a failure, it is anticipated the operational availability will be increased due to the reduction in system downtime attributed to logistics delay. For systems where logistics time is the major contributor to downtime, prognostics may yield large gains in operational availability. This paper provides an analysis of a hypothetical system that implements a prognostics algorithm and examines the system-level gains for different RUL prediction values. The analysis uses the BlockSim and a Monte Carlo-based simulation tool that is able to take multiple redundancies into account when calculating metrics. Finally, two metrics are proposed to help quantify the benefit of prognostics: Relative Downtime Reduction and Relative Availability Gain.

Keywords—*Electronic Prognostics*;

I. INTRODUCTION

Prognostics, comprised of data-driven and model-based algorithms, aims to predict the remaining useful life of a system or a component in a system. This RUL prediction provides valuable information that can influence decisions on how to operate and maintain the system.

Due to the benefits prognostics promises, the Department of Defense is investigating the implementation of Prognostics & Health Management (PHM) on future systems to support its Condition Based Maintenance strategy. As part of the acquisition process for new systems, the government is identifying new requirements and Key Performance Parameters (KPP). These KPPs often include mission performance requirements as well as reliability-centered metrics comprised of Mean Time Between Failure, Mean Down Time, and Operational Availability. Implementing a prognostics algorithm will influence these reliability metrics both at the part-level (where the prognostics is implemented) as well as the system-level; therefore understanding how the system-level reliability-centered metrics will be influenced will be very important to both the government and its contractors so that

realistic prognostics requirements can be written for testing and operational use.

This paper will first show how a prognostics algorithm implementation alters the timeline for an Operational Failure event and includes a general formula for Operational Availability with prognostics. A hypothetical system, consisting of serial and parallel groupings, is then presented as a case study to show how the prognostics implementation alters the reliability metrics of the system. Finally, two metrics are proposed to quantify the system-level improvements from the prognostics algorithm.

II. PROGNOSTICS TIMELINE

In a typical event timeline, the system is fully operational or “up” until a part failure occurs.¹ Once the part fails the system reports itself as “down” or “degraded”. The failed part is then located through Built-In-Testing (BIT) or manual troubleshooting, and a replacement part is ordered, received and then installed to bring the system back to the “up” or fully operational state. This timeline is represented in the top portion of Figure 1.

Implementing a prognostics algorithm provides a predicted RUL value that allows the replacement part to be ordered prior to the part actually failing. By doing so, the experienced total downtime of the system is reduced, thus increasing the availability of the system. This timeline is represented in the bottom portion of Figure 1.

Downtime can be broken into different intervals, summarized in Table 1. The amount of time associated with each of these time periods is heavily dependent on the maintenance philosophy and the situation, and each may be tracked to measure the performance of different pieces of the system’s support structure. For example, the Logistics Delay Time can be relatively short, on the order of an hour, if a replacement part is already available in the supply storeroom or some other local storage facility. Alternatively, if the

¹ This is a general statement. If the part is a single point of failure, this statement is accurate. In the case of a parallel grouping other failures would have had to occur for this statement to be true.

replacement part needs to be manufactured or shipped globally, the Logistics Delay Time can be on the order of days or months.

Typical Event Timeline

Event Timeline with Prognostics

Figure 1. Event timeline with and without Prognostics.

TABLE I: LIST OF TIME PERIOD NAMES

Time Period	DoD Name
Part Fails to Part Ordered	Administrative Delay Time
Part Ordered to Part Received	Logistics Delay Time
Part Received to Part Installed	Repair Time

III. OPERATIONAL AVAILABILITY

Operational Availability, or A_O , is a Key Performance Parameter for Deployed systems and links system reliability (Mean Time Between Failure, MTBF), maintainability (Mean Time To Repair, MTTR), and supportability requirements (Mean Administrative Delay Time, MAdmDT, and Mean Logistics Delay Time, MLDT) into a single metric that is identified first during the design of the system, and is then used as a goal for measuring actual operational performance [1]. The intent of A_O is to reflect the proportion or percentage of time a unit can perform its mission. The A_O equation for a continuously running system is:

$$A_O = \frac{MTBF}{MTBF + MTTR + MAdmDT + MLDT} \quad (1)$$

This formula is general enough that it can be used for individual components as well as systems. Examining the timeline in Figure 1 allows this equation to be altered to account for the implementation of a prognostics algorithm for a single part:

$$A_{O, Prog} = \frac{MTBF}{MTBF + MTTR + \max\{0, MAdmDT + MLDT - RUL\}} \quad (2)$$

MTTR only includes the amount of working time it takes to troubleshoot and repair the system. The system can't be repaired until the part is received, so the MTTR remains unchanged in the denominator. Ordering parts based on the RUL prediction reduces the Administrative and Logistics Delay Times. However, a RUL prediction greater than the combined time of the Administrative Delay and Logistics Delay does not increase the availability of the system, yielding the "maximum" function.

IV. EXAMPLE SYSTEM

To demonstrate the effect on system level metrics, the hypothetical Reliability Block Diagram (RBD) shown in Figure 2 was created. It contains a single serial component followed by a one-of-two parallel group, then a two-of-three parallel group. Such configurations are common where redundant components are necessary to maintain critical functionality. It is assumed that the parts in each individual parallel grouping are identical within the group. Table II contains the assumed Mean Times Between Failure for the different parts. The Exponential Distribution, with the associated MTBFs as their parameter, was used to simulate the up-times of the parts.²

Figure 2: Reliability Block Diagram for a Hypothetical System

TABLE II: Component Mean Time Between Failures

Name	Mean Time Between Failure (hours)
Serial	5000
Parallel Group 1	1500
Parallel Group 2	1000

² Other distributions can be used as well. Exponential has relatively high probability for extreme events (failures near 0 and failures far away from the mean) when compared to other distributions. It is also consistent with Markov-inspired approaches that are common in DoD for reliability analysis. If real world data is available, Kernel Density Estimation or other approaches can be utilized to generate an approximate density function for the failure times.

For simplicity we will only model a single Downtime value that encompasses the Admin Delay, Logistics Delay, and Time to Repair times. The initial downtime is assumed to have a Normal distribution with mean equal to 500 hours and standard deviation equal to 24 hours, causing the vast majority of the downtimes to be between 18 and 24 days. The simulation ran to 100,000 hours with 1,000 runs performed³; system-level metrics, including Availability, System Uptime, System Downtime, and Number of Failures, were calculated and stored. To simulate the implementation of a prognostics algorithm the mean of the downtime was decreased in increments of 24 hours; new system-level metrics were then calculated with the new reduced downtime. The standard deviation was kept constant.

Figure 3 shows the availability of the system for increasing Remaining Useful Life (RUL) predictions. A prognostics algorithm is assumed to be implemented on all components of the system. As expected, the availability increases with greater RUL predictions; in this case the increase is very linear in nature.

Figure 3: RUL Value vs. Ao

Figure 4 shows the number of catastrophic failures the system experiences in the simulation time, as well as the failures from the three sub-groupings.

Figure 4: RUL vs. Failures

³ ReliaSoft’s BlockSim tool for simulating Reliability Block Diagrams.

There are two very interesting points from Figure 4. First, the number of failures from the serial component increases as the RUL estimate is increased. Having a better RUL estimate reduces the downtime, thus decreasing the total time for a failure cycle (uptime plus downtime) for the serial component. Since the simulation runs to a specific end time, the reduction in the total time per failure cycle allows for more failures to occur, yielding the increase in.

The second interesting feature of Figure 4 is the nonlinear, convex decrease in the number of failures coming from the two parallel groupings (note, this shows the number of system-downing failures for the subgroups). This is likely due in large part to the decrease in the probability of failure for the $(n+1)^{th}$ item while the n^{th} replacement is in transit in an n of k parallel grouping. For example, in the second parallel grouping there is a 2 of 3 redundancy. This grouping will only fail if a second component fails while the group has already had one failure. The general equation for this probability is:

$$P(\text{group fails | no more redundancy}) = \int_{t_{rl}}^{t_{sr}} \text{Conditioned Uptime PDF } dt \quad (3)$$

Where t_{rl} is the time in which redundancy was lost due to subcomponent failure and t_{sr} is the time in which the system is restored. The Probability Density Function for the part uptimes, conditioned on the fact that time has reached t_{rl} is then integrated to calculate the probability the parallel grouping will go down. The prognostics algorithm effectively decreases the downtime for the part, reducing t_{sr} , thus decreasing the probability the entire group will fail, and thus decreasing the total number of catastrophic failures at the system level. The Conditioned Uptime PDF will depend not only on the individual uptime distributions of the components that make up the parallel grouping, but also on the number of components that may fail. Therefore the behavior shown in actual systems may be somewhat different from that shown in this example, but a decrease should be expected.

V. METRICS

Extensive research has been performed in determining metrics relevant to quantifying prognostic performance [2]-[5]. However, since systems are composed of multiple components that may or may not have prognostics algorithms in use, it is important to quantify the system-level gains that will be made. To help quantify the gains, two metrics are proposed: Relative Downtime Reduction and Relative Availability Gain. These two metrics focus on different aspects of the reliability of the system, thus shedding light on how different levels of personnel (i.e. Program Manager vice End users) will view the gains made by the prognostics system.

A. Relative Downtime Reduction

Relative Downtime Reduction (RDR), as its name implies, predicts the reduction of downtime associated with system-level failures. This takes a somewhat micro, or unit-centric

perspective since when a system is down it cannot perform its mission. The equation for RDR is below.

$$RDR = \frac{Downtime_{Initial} - Downtime_{With\ Prognostics}}{Downtime_{Initial}} \quad (4)$$

Where $Downtime_{Initial}$ is the Downtime of the system without the prognostics system implemented. Due to it being more unit-centric, RDR can be considered a “tactical” metric. End users operating the system would likely favor this metric.

B. Relative Availability Gain

Relative Availability Gain, or RAG, measures the increase in availability for the system after the implementation of the prognostics algorithm. Availability is especially important when determining the number of required units to perform a specific mission.

For example, a simple approach is to use a Binomial distribution with a Probability of Success equal to the availability, allowing for the calculation of finding the number of units k needed for n units to be usable with probability p . This approach would assume availability is constant in time, ignoring the temporal change of availability and shouldn’t be used in actual applications, but illustrates the concept.

The formula for RAG is shown in equation (5).

$$RAG = \frac{Availability_{Initial} - Availability_{With\ Prognostics}}{Availability_{Initial}} \quad (5)$$

Where $Availability_{Initial}$ is the system’s availability without prognostics implemented. Availability is a metric typically used in higher level planning, it can be thought of as a “strategic” metric. Hence, RAG measures a strategic gain for the prognostics implementation and would likely be favored by programmatic individuals.

Figure 5 below shows both the RAG and the RDR for the example system for the different RUL values.

Figure 5: Relative Availability Gain and Relative Downtime Reduction vs. Remaining Useful Life Estimate

Notice the RDR is consistently larger than the RAG, by approximately a factor of 2 over all the RUL values. This may imply that for this specific implementation the actual users of the system would value the prognostics algorithm much more than individuals that are more programmatic or strategic, which demonstrates a very important concept: no single metric will accurately summarize the performance gains from prognostics, and multiple metrics should be used.

VI. CONCLUSION

As part of System Engineering, Organizations use Key Performance Parameters to measure the performance of their systems. From a reliability standpoint, the implementation of prognostics will influence the system-level Operational Availability, Mean Down Time, and Mean Time Between Failure. In an effort to write informed requirements for prognostics algorithms, these system-level effects must be understood; this understanding can be derived through the use of high-level probability modeling approaches. No single metric can quantify these effects, especially since users at different levels will emphasize different metrics. Relative Availability Gain and Relative Downtime Reduction are two metrics that not only clearly identify the system-level gains of the prognostics algorithm, but also help to get a more complete understanding of the reliability increase from the prognostics algorithm. Both the approach and the metrics described in this paper will aid Organizations in writing attainable prognostic requirements for their systems as well as quantify the system-level gains that will be made from the implementation of a PHM system.

Future work will expand on this hypothetical system to a more representative system. The work will include evaluating a variable MLDT at the component level, relevant time to failure modeling, component degradation/performance impact to system’s expect life and predicted RUL, and incorporate a cost of “lost mission days” to further model the cost reductions from prognostics.

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